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BEYOND INSTITUTIONAL BOUNDARIES

THE ROLE OF INTERNATIONAL ORGANIZATIONS FOR REGULAR, ORDERLY, AND SAFE MIGRATION.

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Policy Statement

International migration emerges from a multifaceted interplay of economic, political, environmental, and social factors, making it a profound global development concern. Millions traverse borders in pursuit of enhanced living conditions, employment opportunities, and safety, while others are compelled to depart due to conflicts, climate change, or persecution. International organizations such as the International Organization for Migration (IOM) and the United Nations High Commissioner for Refugees (UNHCR) are essential in promoting regular, orderly, and safe migration. They establish guidelines that assist nations in safeguarding the human rights of migrants, provide support during transit, and foster cooperation among countries of origin, transit, and destination. Initiatives such as the Global Compact for Safe, Orderly, and Regular Migration aid governments in implementing more equitable and inclusive policies.

In addition to establishing global policies, these organizations enhance institutional capacities within countries to address migration challenges. They offer technical assistance, promote the exchange of best practices, and support infrastructure development conducive to welcoming migrants and refugees. Such initiatives are crucial for preventing human trafficking, reducing the risks associated with irregular migration, and facilitating the social and economic integration of migrants into host communities. For example, the IOM conducts training sessions for humanitarian workers and public officials while collaborating with civil society and the private sector, thereby broadening the impact of its initiatives.

Background

The global migration phenomenon has intensified significantly in recent decades, with millions of people moving in search of better living conditions and security or to escape humanitarian crises. According to the International Organization for Migration (IOM), there were approximately 281 million international migrants in 2020, representing 3.6% of the world's population, a growth from 2.8% recorded in 2000 (IOM, 2020). This increase reflects a range of factors, from political and economic crises to climate change and armed conflict. In particular, climate change has led to forced migrations, as populations are compelled to leave their lands due to natural disasters and environmental degradation. These migratory flows, however, often expose migrants to situations of vulnerability where their rights may be overlooked.

Given the complexity and scale of this phenomenon, the United Nations, through the International Organization for Migration (IOM), plays a crucial role in promoting a coordinated and structured approach to migration. IOM aims to ensure regular, orderly, and safe migration while addressing the humanitarian needs of migrants and strengthening international cooperation for migration management. The UN 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development, particularly Sustainable Development Goal 10.7, underscores the importance of facilitating migration and mobility safely and responsibly while promoting planned and well-managed migration policies (UN, 2015). This global agenda recognizes migration as an essential element of sustainable development, encouraging countries to adopt policies that respect human rights and promote the social inclusion of migrants.

In addition, the Global Compact for Safe, Orderly, and Regular Migration, adopted by the United Nations General Assembly in 2018, represents a significant milestone for migration governance. This pact establishes 23 objectives aimed at addressing the challenges of international migration, among which the promotion of regular migration pathways and the fight against trafficking in persons stand out (UN, 2018). However, the practical implementation of these goals varies among countries and depends on each country's ability to align its domestic policies with the principles of the Compact. The IOM and other UN agencies, such as the United Nations High Commissioner for Refugees (UNHCR), have supported national governments with technical assistance, training, and monitoring so that the guidelines of the pact can be put into practice.

These actions seek to promote migration in a way that respects the dignity and rights of migrants and contributes to the stability and development of countries of origin, transit, and destination. Over the past few years, IOM and other international organizations have been working with countries on several fronts, from preventing irregular migration and providing humanitarian support to facilitating the socio-economic integration of migrants into their new communities. Cooperation initiatives between countries, such as creating safe pathways for migration and developing campaigns against xenophobia, are essential to ensuring that the migratory phenomenon benefits all. By addressing the challenges and seizing migration opportunities, these organizations help build fairer, more inclusive, and more sustainable migration governance for the future (IOM, 2020; UNHCR, 2019).

The 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development, adopted by the United Nations in 2015, recognizes the importance of migration in global development.

Sustainable Development Goal (SDG) 10.7, in particular, reinforces the commitment to facilitate safe, orderly, and responsible migration by implementing planned and well-managed migration policies (UN, 2015). This objective recognizes migration as a means of reducing inequalities, allowing people to seek better living conditions and contribute to developing the economies and societies of the destination countries. In this way, SDG 10.7 underscores the need to ensure that the rights of migrants are protected and that they can contribute positively to the social and economic development of both their countries of origin and destination.

In conjunction with the 2030 Agenda, the Global Compact for Safe, Orderly, and Regular Migration, adopted by the United Nations General Assembly in 2018, signifies a considerable advance in establishing international migration guidelines. This compact was formulated to respond to the challenges of irregular migration and aims to address the issues affecting millions of migrants and countries globally (UN, 2018). With a comprehensive set of 23 objectives, the pact endeavors to promote regular and secure migration pathways, safeguard the rights of migrants, and combat trafficking and exploitation. These objectives encompass the collection and utilization of precise migration data, the enhancement of migrant protection services, and the bolstering of international cooperation to tackle the root causes of forced migration. Consequently, the pact establishes a vital framework for collaboration among countries of origin, transit, and destination, intending to develop an integrated and balanced approach to migration management.

The commitments articulated in the Global Compact underscore the necessity to enhance international and regional cooperation in addressing migration challenges holistically and inclusively. To achieve this objective, international organizations such as the International Organization for Migration (IOM) and the United Nations High Commissioner for Refugees (UNHCR) assume a critical role in assisting countries with implementing the pact's objectives. For instance, IOM offers technical assistance and capacity-building initiatives that enable nations to formulate policies that uphold human rights and promote safe and dignified migration. Furthermore, these organizations collaborate with civil society and the private sector, thereby fostering partnerships that amplify the effectiveness of migration policies and advance the social inclusion of migrants (IOM, 2020; UNHCR, 2019).

Nevertheless, the practical implementation of the goals outlined in the Global Compact exhibits significant variation among different nations, with numerous countries facing

considerable challenges in aligning their domestic policies with established international guidelines. In several states, persistent political and economic challenges and insufficient infrastructure hinder the effective execution of measures essential for migration management. For instance, the COVID-19 pandemic has intensified these obstacles by imposing mobility restrictions and increasing the vulnerability of migrant populations (IOM, 2020). In this context, the international community must enhance cooperation mechanisms and allocate resources toward solutions that facilitate the integration of migrants while upholding their dignity. As the global community advances toward a more coordinated and human rights-centered approach to migration governance, the Global Compact and the 2030 Agenda serve as pivotal frameworks for cultivating a more inclusive and equitable future.

Findings

Since 2020, the United Nations High Commissioner for Refugees (UNHCR) and the International Organization for Migration (IOM) have markedly escalated their initiatives aimed at supporting migrants and refugees across various regions, with a particular emphasis on Venezuelan refugees and individuals displaced internally as a result of global conflicts and the COVID-19 pandemic. As of 2023, it is projected that in excess of 110 million individuals have been compelled to abandon their homes due to conflicts and humanitarian crises. This statistic encompasses 35 million refugees and 62.5 million internally displaced persons. Since the onset of the Venezuelan crisis, IOM and UNHCR have dedicated approximately US\$ 1.44 billion to address the requirements of Venezuelan refugees and their host communities across 17 countries in Latin America and the Caribbean, facilitating access to shelter, food security, healthcare, and social integration services (AGÊNCIA BRASIL, 2023; THE UNITED NATIONS IN BRAZIL, 2023).

In Colombia, for instance, the United Nations High Commissioner for Refugees (UNHCR) and the International Organization for Migration (IOM) collaborate to deliver medical and psychological assistance, as well as professional training programs, aimed at integrating Venezuelan refugees into the local workforce. In Brazil, initiatives such as Operation Welcome, which is supported by UNHCR, endeavor to assimilate Venezuelan migrants into society through resettlement and migration regularization programs. These initiatives contribute to reducing the vulnerabilities faced by migrants by providing them with more dignified and sustainable living options in their host countries (IOM BRAZIL, 2023).

In Europe, the conflict in Ukraine has precipitated one of the largest influxes of refugees on the continent since World War II, with over five million Ukrainians seeking asylum in neighboring countries. The United Nations High Commissioner for Refugees (UNHCR) and the International Organization for Migration (IOM) have been actively engaged in providing immediate humanitarian assistance in nations such as Poland and Moldova. This assistance encompasses temporary shelter, access to medical services, and psychological support. It is crucial for helping refugees address war-related trauma, acclimatize to new environments, and facilitate their integration into local communities (UNHCR, 2023).

Concerning sustainability, the International Organization for Migration (IOM) has instituted programs to provide emergency response and long-term solutions, including the education and professional training of migrants and refugees. These initiatives are implemented in sub-Saharan African nations, including Uganda and Kenya, where refugees are afforded vocational training designed to enhance their self-sufficiency and facilitate their economic integration into the local market. This methodology contributes to diminishing reliance on ongoing humanitarian assistance, thereby fostering financial inclusion and social cohesion (United Nations in Brazil, 2023).

As a result, the United Nations High Commissioner for Refugees (UNHCR) and the International Organization for Migration (IOM) have taken on the monumental task of addressing the complex dynamics of migration and refugee movements. Their goal is to foster coordinated measures that safeguard and assist migrants. By integrating emergency relief and sustainable development initiatives, these organizations aim to establish a more inclusive and resilient framework for migration governance on a global scale.

Recommendations

To strengthen the role of international organizations in migration, it is recommended that:

- **Foster international and regional cooperation through the encouragement of harmonized migration policies.** The harmonization of such policies facilitates the mobility and integration of migrants, ensuring their access to essential services, including healthcare and education, while effectively combating issues such as human trafficking (D'Angelo, 2020). Moreover, this cooperation enables the

- exchange of information and effective practices, thereby enhancing migration management in a humanitarian manner, supported by international organizations such as the International Organization for Migration (IOM) (Mastrorillo et al., 2021). Consequently, by aligning their policies, countries not only bolster the safety and security of migrants but also derive economic and social benefits by fostering migration that contributes positively to all stakeholders involved (UNHCR, 2022; IOM, 2021).
- **Increase funding for programs designed to support migrants and host communities.** With sufficient resources, governments and international organizations can implement initiatives that address the fundamental needs of migrants, including access to food, housing, healthcare, and education, particularly in crisis contexts where they experience precarious conditions (Gonzalez, 2023). Furthermore, funding is crucial for the expansion of resettlement and integration initiatives, which provide language courses and professional training that facilitate the adaptation of migrants and enhance their contributions to the socio-economic development of the regions that accommodate them (Gonzalez, 2023). Investing in host communities is essential to fostering harmonious coexistence and directing resources toward infrastructure, public service improvements, and initiatives that combat xenophobia (Bohra-Mishra & Massey, 2020).
- **Establish comprehensive monitoring systems to evaluate the efficacy of migration policies.** These systems should accumulate and analyze quantitative and qualitative data, encompassing indicators such as migration rates, social integration, and access to essential services (Carrillo, 2021). Implementing robust mechanisms enables governments to discern strengths and deficiencies in their policies, facilitating continuous adjustments. Furthermore, the transparency and accountability engendered by these systems cultivate trust among migrants, local communities, and authorities, thereby ensuring equitable policy execution (Carling, 2020). With precise data, policymakers are better equipped to comprehend the experiences and challenges migrants face, allowing for the adaptation of policies to address the needs of vulnerable groups, including women and children (UNHCR, 2022; IOM, 2023).
- **It is essential to invest in awareness-raising campaigns aimed at combating xenophobia and fostering a positive perspective on migration is critical.** These campaigns play a crucial role in creating a supportive environment for migrants.

- Xenophobia, frequently exacerbated by misinformation, has the potential to result in discrimination and social exclusion, adversely affecting both migrants and host communities (Mastrorillo et al., 2021). Well-crafted campaigns can effectively demystify negative stereotypes by showcasing the contributions of migrants to the economy, culture, and social diversity of their host countries (Gonzalez, 2023). Beyond their educational objectives, these initiatives can advocate for the development of fairer public policies; an enhanced public perception of migration will likely increase the probability that authorities will implement inclusive policies (UNHCR, 2023). By engaging local leaders and promoting interaction between migrants and residents through cultural dialogues and events, these campaigns address xenophobia and cultivate an environment where migration is perceived as an opportunity for cultural enrichment and social development, ultimately benefiting society as a whole (IOM, 2023).

Final Considerations

Migration, characterized by regularity, order, and safety, represents a multifaceted phenomenon that necessitates coordinated efforts among countries of origin, transit, and destination. To effectively manage migration flows, governments, and international organizations must engage in collaborative initiatives to foster migration policies that uphold human rights and ensure the safety of migrants. This encompasses the implementation of adaptable visa systems, the establishment of secure migration routes, and the safeguarding of migrant workers' rights. Furthermore, tailoring policies to accommodate local and regional realities while considering economic, social, and cultural factors enhances the safe movement of individuals, aids in alleviating humanitarian crises, and addresses issues such as human trafficking.

Furthermore, the sustainability of migration initiatives is contingent upon a sustained commitment to economic and social development within the countries of origin of migrants. It is imperative to invest in programs addressing the root causes of migration, such as poverty and violence, to establish conditions that encourage individuals to remain in their communities. International collaboration is essential in providing technical and financial support for initiatives to foster sustainable development and job creation. The involvement of local communities in the planning and implementation of migration policies is crucial to ensure that the perspectives of both migrants and citizens are acknowledged, thereby establishing a virtuous cycle that enhances regular and secure migration.

International organizations, including the International Organization for Migration (IOM) and the United Nations High Commissioner for Refugees (UNHCR), have been pivotal in advancing migration governance that upholds human rights and fosters social inclusion. These entities have developed comprehensive guidelines and established a normative framework, exemplified by the Global Compact for Safe, Orderly, and Regular Migration and the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), which assist states in formulating more humanitarian and inclusive policies. Nonetheless, the efficacy of these agreements hinges upon the sustained dedication of national governments and civil society to their execution, necessitating the translation of guidelines into actionable national policies.

Implementing the principles established within the global compacts presents a multifaceted challenge requiring the engagement of multiple stakeholders. Governments are mandated to commit to the adoption of laws and policies that are congruent with international obligations, as well as to invest in programs and infrastructure that safeguard the rights of migrants. This necessity encompasses the development of mechanisms designed to monitor the situations of migrants and to allocate sufficient resources. Furthermore, collaboration among various ministries and governmental levels is crucial to ensure an integrated approach that addresses the diverse dimensions of migration, encompassing both security and economic development.

In conclusion, the establishment of global migration governance that upholds human rights and fosters social inclusion presents considerable challenges, including economic and political disparities among nations. The rise of anti-immigration rhetoric, particularly from an increasingly influential far-right movement, poses obstacles to the acceptance of inclusive and humanitarian policies. However, it is imperative for international organizations to promote dialogue and cooperation among countries, advocating for the implementation of policies that perceive migration not as a threat, but as a significant opportunity for development. This optimistic perspective can guide our efforts toward a more inclusive and prosperous future.

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